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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A STABILITY-
INDICATING ZERO AND FIRST ORDER UV
SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR EPROSARTN
MESYLEATE IN BULK AND TABLETS**¹Mr. Shahzad Ahmed*, ²Dr. Aquil-ur-Rahim Siddiquei¹JMCT Institute of pharmacy, Wadala road, Dist: Nashik 422006 (M.S.),²Bhagwan College of Pharmacy, Aurangabad**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Two simple, rapid, sensitive and accurate stability indicating Zero order UV-Spectrophotometric and first order derivative methods have been developed for estimation of eprosartan mesyleate in bulk and tablets. Methanol: water (2:8) was used as a solvent. In UV Spectrophotometric method absorbance of samples are recorded at 234 nm. In first order derivative method the amplitude of trough was recorded at 244 nm. Eprosartan mesyleate follows linearity in the concentration range of 2-30 µg/ml. Assay results were in good agreement with label claim. The drug was subjected to acid, alkali and neutral hydrolysis, oxidation, dry heat, UV light and photolytic degradation. The proposed method for stability study shows that there was appreciable degradation found in stress condition of eprosartan mesyleate. These methods were validated statistically and recovery studies.

Key words: Eprosartan mesyleate (EM), UV-Spectrophotometer, First order derivative, Stability studies.

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INTRODUCTION:

Eprosartan mesylate (EM), (E)-2-butyl-1-(p-carboxybenzyl)- α -2-thenylimidazole-5-acrylic acid methane sulphonate, [Fig.1] is an angiotensin-II-receptor antagonist (ARA-II) with actions similar to those of losartan [1-3]. Its molecular weight is 520.61832 [g/mol] with molecular formula $C_{24}H_{28}N_2O_7S_2$. It is used in the management of hypertension. EM is not official in any pharmacopoeia. Literature survey reveals few reported methods for the determination of EM including HPLC methods along with other angiotensin-II receptor antagonist group, [4,5]RP-HPLC for simultaneous estimation along with Hydrochlorothiazide [6] and few Chromatographic methods [7-10] for the determination of Eprosartan mesylate in biological fluids.

According to our knowledge no method has been reported for Eprosartan mesylate estimation by spectroscopic method. The present work deals with estimation of Eprosartan mesylate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation by simple and derivative spectroscopy which is economical and intended for better reproducibility of product.

Fig.No. 1: Structure of Eprosartan mesylate

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Reagents**

All reagents used were of analytical grade

INSTRUMENTATION

SHIMADZU AUX – 120 (Weighing Balance)
 UV Shimadzu 1800 (PC Series)
 UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer
 Software UV Probe 2.21
 Matched quartz cells 1 cm
 Wavelength range 190 -900 nm
 Lamp: 50 w, Deuterium Lamp
 Detector: Silicon Photodiode
 Cell holder: 1 mm wide, 12 mm high
 Resolution: 1 nm
 Micropipette (20 – 200 μ l)

PROCEDURE**Preparation of Standard Stock Solution and Study of Calibration Curve**

Standard stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of Eprosartan Mesylate in 20 ml of methanol

in 100 ml volumetric flask. Volume was adjusted with water upto mark to get the concentration of 100 μ g/ml solution. Different aliquots were taken from the stock solution, diluted upto 10 ml mark with water to obtain the series of concentrations. The solutions were scanned on spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800) in the UV range of 200-400 nm. Eprosartan shows maximum absorbance at 234 nm (Fig: 2). The same spectra were derivetised into first order derivative, using UV probe software of the instrument, where $\Delta\lambda = 2$ (Fig: 3). The amplitudes of the corresponding troughs were measured at 244 nm. In both methods, drug follows linearity in the concentration range 2-30 μ g/ml. The optical characteristics and linear regression data for calibration curve is summarized in Table 1. Calibration curve at 234 and 244 nm is plotted Absorbance Vs Concentration (Fig. 6 and Fig. 7)

Preparation of sample solution

For analysis of commercial formulation; twenty tablets were weighted, mean weight determined and crushed into fine powder. An accurately weighed quantity of powder equivalent to 5 mg of Eprosartan was transferred in to 100 ml volumetric flask containing 20 ml of methanol, shaken manually for 10 min., volume was adjusted with water and filtered through Whatmann filter paper no 41. After appropriate dilutions of samples; in UV spectrophotometry method, absorbance was recorded at 234 nm and in first order derivative method amplitude of troughs was recorded at 244 nm. The concentrations of the drug were calculated from linear regression equation; results are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Recovery Studies

Recovery experiments were carried out by adding known amount of drug solution to pre-analysed samples at three different levels i.e. 80%, 100% and 120% and reanalysed it by the proposed methods. The percentage recoveries were calculated; the results are summarized in Table 4.

Stability Studies

The API is subjected to a number of force degradation conditions which include acidic, basic, and oxidative conditions. Force degradation should be one of the activities performed early in the development process to ensure that the method is discriminating between the API and degradants. Depending on the API, not every stress agent may effect degradation, but each agent has to be evaluated to determine whether degradation occurs.

Accurately weighed 10 mg bulk drug was taken in 10 ml volumetric flask. Then the volume was made with 0.1 N NaOH and refluxed for 5 h at 60°. The absorbance was measured in every hour by withdrawing the required amount of sample from the reaction mixture to prepare 10 μ g/ml

concentrations and subjected for UV analysis. Similarly, acidic and neutral degradation were performed and subjected to analysis keeping the condition same as earlier by taking 0.1 N HCl and distilled water as medium respectively. About 10 mg of bulk drug was weighed accurately, 2-3 drops of methanol: water (2:8) was added to make the drug soluble and finally the volume was made up to 10 ml by using 3% H₂O₂. The above solution mixture was kept in dark condition for 12 h. Each 6 h interval the specified amount sample was withdrawn and the required concentration was prepared and determined the absorbance. For photolytic degradation about 150 mg of bulk drug was accurately weighed and kept in the Petri dish under direct sun light for three days. After each 6 h interval the required amount of sample was withdrawn to prepare the concentration of 10 µg/ml by using solvent system and then absorbance was measured. A specific amount of bulk drug was taken in a cleaned Petri dish and was put it in an oven at 60° for determining thermal degradation. The UV-degradation was performed by keeping the API in UV light and after each 8 h interval the sample was withdrawn and required concentration (10µg/ml) was made for measuring absorbance in UV spectrophotometer. In all cases the extensive degradation were found but the magnitude of degradation was in the order of alkaline>oxidative>acidic>neutral> thermal>photolytic>UV.

Eprosartan Mesylate was found to be highly sensitive to alkaline, oxidative and acidic degradation condition. The summary of degradation is given in Table 6. Fig. 3 to Fig. 5 showing Acidic, Oxidative and Alkaline degradation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Eprosartan Mesylate in methanol: water (20:80) solvent system showed absorbance maximum at 234 nm. In 'first order derivative' the amplitude of trough was recorded at 244 nm. In both the methods Eprosartan mesylate follows linearity in the concentration range 2-30 µg/ml. Amount of drug determined was in the good agreement with the label claim. The methods were validated for accuracy, precision and ruggedness. Accuracy of the methods was assessed by recovery studies. In both the methods, as %RSD values were found to be less than 2, indicative of accuracy of the method. Precision of the methods was studied as intra-day, inter-day and repeatability. The %RSD values less than 2 indicate the methods are precise. Ruggedness of the proposed methods was studied with the help of two analysts, the %RSD value less than 2 indicate methods are rugged. The results from validation studies are shown in Table 5. Both these methods are simple, rapid and accurate and precise and can be used for routine analysis of Eprosartan from tablet formulations.

Table 1. Linear regression data for the calibration curves^a

Parameter	At 234 nm	At 244 nm
Linearity equation (Y= a+ bc)	Y=0.042X+0.019	0.0187X+ 0.003
Range (µg/mL)	2.00-30.00	2.00-30.00
Correlation Coefficient(r ²)	0.9993	0.9997
Chi Square	0.00544	0.00117
Std. Error of Estimation	0.01242	0.00501

Table 2. Intra- and inter-day precision of spectroscopy method^a at 234 nm

Amount (µg/mL)	Intra-day precision			Inter-day precision		
	Mean Absorbance	S. D.	%R. S. D.	Mean Absorbance	S. D.	%R. S. D.
6	0.2700	0.0056	2.0621	0.2747	0.0065	2.3688
8	0.3580	0.0089	2.4827	0.3540	0.0062	1.7641
10	0.4280	0.0089	2.0767	0.4320	0.0060	1.3889
12	0.5270	0.0066	1.2443	0.5250	0.0066	1.2490
14	0.5913	0.0070	1.1878	0.5977	0.0051	0.8586
16	0.7010	0.0030	0.4280	0.7027	0.0045	0.6417
18	0.7727	0.0090	1.1672	0.7783	0.0065	0.8359

^an=6

Table 3. Intra- and inter-day precision of derivative spectroscopy method^a at 244 nm

Amount ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Intra-day precision			Inter-day precision		
	Mean Absorbance	S. D.	%R. S. D.	Mean Absorbance	S. D.	%R. S. D.
6	0.1157	0.0076	6.5463	0.1150	0.0060	5.2174
8	0.1613	0.0070	4.3536	0.1490	0.0056	3.7368
10	0.2017	0.0031	1.5149	0.1893	0.0055	2.9089
12	0.2280	0.0066	2.8761	0.2253	0.0051	2.2773
14	0.2640	0.0046	1.7358	0.2517	0.0035	1.3955
16	0.3140	0.0070	2.2293	0.2937	0.0075	2.5558
18	0.3363	0.0055	1.6375	0.3300	0.0075	2.2878

^a $n=6$ **Table 4. Recovery studies^afor derivative spectroscopy**

Excess drug added to ^b the analyte (%)	Amount recovered(mg)	Recovery (%)	%R.S.D
0	10.04	100.54	0.75
80	18.07	100.21	0.95
100	20.04	99.79	0.44
120	22.06	100.06	0.80

^a $n=6$, ^b Matrix containing 400 mg drug.**Table 5. Summary of validation parameters**

Parameter	234 nm	244 nm
Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	2-30	2-30
Correlation coefficient	0.9993	0.9997
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.2797	2.2
Limit of quantitation ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.8476	6.66
Recovery ($n = 6$)	100.21	100.15
Precision (%R.S.D.)		
Repeatability of application ($n = 6$)	1.30	1.45
Repeatability of measurement ($n = 6$)		
Inter-day ($n = 6$)	1.30	1.39
Intra-day ($n = 6$)	1.52	1.14
Specificity	specific	Specific

Table 6. Summary of Stress Degradation Results

Stressed condition	Time	% of assay of degraded product	% assay of active substance
Alkaline Hydrolysis (1N NaOH)	5 h	34.9	65.1
Oxidative Degradation	6 h	27.7	72.3
Acidic Hydrolysis (1N HCL)	5 h	21.4	78.6
Neutral Hydrolysis	5 h	17.8	82.2
Photo Degradation	12 h	15.6	84.4
UV Degradation	48 h	14.2	85.8
Thermal Degradation	12 h	13.9	86.1

Fig. 2; UV Spectra of Eprosartan Mesylate at 234 nm 10 ppm

Fig. 3; UV Spectra of Eprosartan Mesylate in Methanol: Water (2:8) at 244 nm

Fig. 3; UV Spectra of Eprosartan Mesylate at 234 nm 10 ppm in acidic condition

Fig: 4; UV Spectra of Eprosartan Mesylate at 234 nm 10 ppm in oxidative condition

Fig: 5; UV Spectra of Eprosartan Mesylate at 234 nm 10 ppm in alkaline condition

$$y = 0.042x + 0.019$$

$$R^2 = 0.9993$$

Fig: No.; 6: Linearity Graph at 234 nm

Fig: No.; 7: Linearity Graph at 244 nm

CONCLUSION:

Various reported for the estimation of EPM require highly sophisticated instruments, costly solvents, time consuming when compared to UV Spectrophotometric method. Also, the better precision and accuracy was achieved than the reported methods. Thus, the proposed method is precise, accurate and simple to perform. It is rapid and does not require any expensive or sophisticated apparatus, in contrast with chromatographic techniques. Hence, the proposed method UV Spectrophotometric method can be effectively used for the routine analysis of EPM bulk and Tablet dosage form. A new simple analytical method was developed to be applied for the evaluation of the stability of EPM to quantify EPM and its degradation products in a solid dosage forms. In addition to demonstrate specificity, forced degradation study can be used to determine the degradation pathways and degradation product of the APIs that could form during storage and facilitate formulation, development, manufacturing and packaging.

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